

Heal Talk

Endo

Talk

Minimal Invasive Endodontics- II

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Minimally Invasive Access Strategies

Root canal anatomy and the complexity of human pulpal systems provide significant challenges for endodontic therapy. The first priority of effective therapy is to access, shape and clean the system in a manner that will allow efficient and total filling of the root canal space, while leaving the tooth with sufficient strength to function successfully.

For almost a century endodontic textbooks have taught the student of dentistry to expose the pulp chambers of teeth with 'straight-line' access to the orifice(s) of the root canal. Access cavities were to be prepared and expanded so that their smallest dimensions were dictated by the separation of the orifices on the pulpal floor and their widest dimensions were at the occlusal. In this era of enhanced lighting and magnification, as well as highly flexible rotary instruments, this approach to a doctrinaire access paradigm is being questioned as perhaps overly invasive of the tooth and an approach that may condemn a tooth to structural failure.

Recently, maintaining structural integrity of the peri-cervical area of the tooth (about four mm above and below the alveolar crest) has been emphasised. Maintenance of the peri-cervical dentin (PCD), especially in molars is felt to be critical to their long-term survivability and optimum function. It acts as the neck of the tooth and transfers masticatory forces to the root and the bone. Thus, the dentin surrounding the alveolar crest is often regarded as the "Irreplaceable Critical Most Zone", the dentin near the alveolar crest is not replaceable and is sacred. Peri Cingulum Dentine is the term used for this critical landmark in the anterior teeth. the term Directed Dentine Conservation was coined in relation to the preservation of PCD as the survival rate increases with its preservation proportionately. Some argue that in treatment planning for endodontics, on a molar tooth especially, clinicians must consider the significantly higher overall compressive forces that create a situation requiring a different set of rules for the calculation of ferrule, post and core design, resistance to fracturing, and most importantly, endodontic access and removal of radicular dentin during endodontic shaping.

In keeping with this philosophy of minimal invasion of bulk dentin structure, the use of round burs and Gates-Glidden burs is now discouraged. While both of these types of instruments have been essential in endodontics for decades, they are now recognised in endodontic treatment as instruments that commonly gouge the endodontic access and the coronal third of the root canal, those areas adjacent to the cemento-enamel junction (CEJ) of the tooth with critical structural prerequisites. Gouging of the access and coronal

canal space must be avoided in order to preserve maximal resistance to structural flexure and ultimate failure. By directing the conservation of dentin and protecting dentin above and below the PCD the practitioner ensures a more viable and proven method to reinforce the endodontically treated tooth. No man-made material or technique can compensate for tooth structure lost in those key areas.

Shaping of the Root Canal Space

Root canals are sometimes depicted as smooth hollow tubes that are more or less tapered in shape. These misleading images do not reflect the intricate anatomical structure and complexity of root canal systems. They are often asymmetrical or oval in cross section, they branch, dilacerate and divide and the canal walls show concavities and convexities. Complex root canal anatomy should be considered one of the most significant challenges in creating root canal shapes that will support good obturation outcomes and leave sufficient remaining strength in the root. After biomechanical instrumentation, the completed root canal shapes need to withstand the internal compressive forces of obturation; provide sufficient resistance form to contain softened and compressible filling materials and retain enough strength for mastication.

Consequently, current shaping strategies employed by today's clinicians align with two general trends in contemporary endodontic practice. A significant number of practitioners believe that enhanced apical instrumentation and larger apical diameters with minimal taper in the canal shape leads to weakening of the root structure and a loss of control over the obturation component of treatment. They advocate smaller apical preparations, continuous taper, and a preparation that promotes resistance form, a tight apical seal and a conservative approach to creating sufficient shape for adequate disinfection. Smaller apical sizes preserve dentin. The arguments are strategic and technique-driven, albeit often supported by inferred outcomes. The impetus for smaller apical sizes has been directed at the disinfection and obturation phase of endodontic therapy.

On the other hand, there is a significant body of literature that presents evidence that larger apical canal diameters are important to shape the apical canal wall, flush debris, allow deeper irrigation to the terminus and decrease remaining bacterial contamination in the system. Studies vary on which size diameter will accomplish maximum cleaning. Some researchers have suggested file diameters ranging from #35-#45 to accomplish significant bacterial reduction. Others have shown that minimal sizes can accomplish this task as adequately as larger diameters. What is remarkably clear from the evidence is that no matter which school of thought one ascribes to, it

is not possible that any apical preparation technique will render the terminus entirely free of bacterial contamination in an infected canal. In essence, structural considerations in shaping continue to remain a compelling argument for conservative shapes.

There is now a large body of conclusive research quantifying the use of rotary and hand nickel-titanium instruments first described by Walia, who report that the use of this super-elastic metal alloy offers less straightening and better centered preparations compared to traditional stainless steel instruments in preparing the wide range of anatomical variability seen in teeth.

These studies have focused on the geometry of shape produced by these instruments alone or in combination with stainless steel; including conicity, taper, flow and maintenance of original canal position. Most of these studies have recorded the degree of change from original position and have measured the loss of original canal positions based on the definitions by Weine. In comparing stainless steel versus nickel-titanium, researchers have focused on both the metallurgy of the systems and the systems themselves. Collectively these studies suggest that Nickel-titanium technology alone or in combination with the conservative use of stainless steel instruments provides shapes that are better centered, maintaining the original canal positions with greater conservation of dentin and safer radicular preparations.

Disinfection and Other Considerations in Minimally Invasive Endodontics

In order to address the microbiologic aetiology of endodontic disease, that is, periapical inflammation, disinfection is and will always remain, a key element of the overall treatment strategy. At first glance, any minimally invasive approach to root canal treatment is at conflict with disinfection.

Current cleaning and shaping methods appear to be unlikely to predictably remove all bio-burden from the root canal system. Therefore, and particularly under the conditions of smaller apical preparation sizes, the search continues for techniques to enhance irrigation efficacy. The possibilities for physical means that enable enhanced disinfection vary from ultrasonic or sonic activation up to and including laser activation.

The effect of a modified access cavity design has only recently been tested in extracted teeth. Using a combined micro-computed tomography and load-to-failure approach, Krishan et al found that in premolars shaping was not impacted and load to failure was significantly higher for teeth with minimal access cavity designs.

Another aspect of this discussion is the finding of micro-cracks induced by various rotary shaping procedures in canal preparation. In recent years several investigations have illustrated such micro-cracks in extracted teeth. While it is not clear at this point if such cracks are generated in vivo, it may be reasonable to develop instruments that reduce vibration and rotational stresses during intracanal procedures in an effort to lessen additional loads on a structurally weakened root.

Micro-computed tomography studies not only show overall canal shaping outcomes but have also demonstrated that hard tissue debris is compacted into unshaped canal areas rendering them potentially inaccessible to irrigation. It is likely future root canal preparation techniques will have to focus on balancing disinfection capacity and iatrogenic damage with enhanced debridement and disinfection.

Restoration Strategies for Maximum Protection and Minimal Invasion

Patients are not well served if the endodontic treatment is successful but the tooth fails, especially with the emergence of implants into the mainstream of dentistry and their choice as an alternative to saving the natural dentition. In extensive reviews of evidence surro-

unding the restoration of endodontically treated teeth, preserving intact coronal and radicular tooth structure, especially maintaining the peri-cervical structure to allow a substantial 'ferrule effect', is considered to be crucial for the optimal biomechanical behaviour of restored teeth. Encircling the parallel walls of remaining dentin with the crown margin allows a ferrule that provides a protective effect by reducing stresses within a tooth. The presence of a 1.5 to 2 mm ferrule has a positive effect on fracture resistance of endodontically treated teeth. Teeth with a ferrule of one mm of vertical tooth structure doubled the resistance to fracture compared with teeth restored without a ferrule. Even if the clinical situation does not permit a circumferential ferrule, an incomplete ferrule is considered a better option than a complete lack of ferrule. However, it can be generally concluded that providing an adequate ferrule lessens the destabilising impact of the post and core system and the final restoration in the long-term performance of restored root treated teeth.

When it comes to severely damaged teeth with little or no coronal structure, in order to provide space for a ferrule, orthodontic extrusion should be considered rather than surgical crown lengthening. This approach preserves more tooth structure and ensures a more favourable biomechanical behaviour of remaining dentin structure. If neither of the alternative methods for providing a ferrule for the restoration can be performed, currently available evidence suggests that a poor treatment outcome and the ultimate loss of the tooth has a high probability.

Is Root Strengthening A Possibility?

The past decade has seen a considerable change in clinical strategies for using and placing posts. An advancing principle promoting minimally invasive therapy directs the nominal use of posts in endodontically treated teeth. That principle, based on evidence, affirms that retaining tooth structure is more valuable than the use of a post in almost every circumstance where adequate structure exists for a ferrule. The long-term success of endodontic treatment has always been highly dependent on the restorative treatment that follows. A restored tooth must be structurally sound and the sealed state of the root canal system must be maintained. Most endodontically treated teeth today are restored with adhesive materials. Adhesive bonding provides an immediate seal of the pulpal spaces and some immediate toughening of the tooth. These materials are generally not dependent on gross mechanical retention, so tooth structure can be preserved and these materials can certainly be termed minimally invasive.

Conventional thought has been that posts do not 'reinforce' the root. Early restorative protocols considered this true for metal posts, but there is now a growing body of evidence that bonded fibre posts can be placed with no removal of dentin structure, may protect the root and make it more resistant to fracture. Fibre-reinforced resin posts were introduced over 20 years ago with the intent to provide more elastic support to the core. The reduced stress transfer to tooth structure lowered the likelihood of root fracture. In addition, posts made of materials with a modulus of elasticity similar to dentin were considered more resilient; able to absorb similar impact forces, and distribute the forces of mastication in a more protective manner to remaining dentin than stiffer metallic posts. Based on the aforementioned evidence, it may be premature to describe adhesive technology as 'reinforcing' or 'root strengthening' but in terms of distributing forces throughout the remaining dentin structure it may certainly be deemed 'protective'.

(It's a review of literature and not an original article)